

JUXTAPOSING CONVENTIONAL AND CONTEMPORARY METHODS OF VALUATION: AN ALTERNATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract

Valuation is referred to as “an art or a science” but this is because of the technique employed to calculate value and not the underlying concept itself. Valuation is the process of determining the worth of a particular interest in land at a particular place and for a particular purpose. Yet, such process of determining value could be affected by uncertainties. The uncertainty and the accuracy of valuation could be as a result of the method and the kind of parameters adopted either implicit or explicit manner. The conventional and contemporary methods of valuation are not devoid of flaws, there are three (3) distinctive observations by valuers which is summarized as follows, firstly that although both methods rely on making assumptions, the assumptions made in contemporary method through the use of DCF are largely unforeseeable, which could affect the accuracy of such valuation. The second observation deals with the challenges set by the conventional method through the use of ARY which is adjusted for term and reversion and assumed to have taken care of all other possible variables i.e Review period (t) and the third observation sets out that both methods have their strengths and weaknesses.

Key words; Conventional method, Contemporary Method, All Risk Yield, Equated Yield.

I. Introduction

We have two types of valuation; Statutory and non-statutory valuation on the other hand we have two types of method of valuation which are Conventional or Traditional and Contemporary or modern methods of valuation (Grosen, A., & Jorgensen, 2000). The common examples of conventional method of valuation are Term and Reversion method and Layer or Hardcore Method (Olayonwa, 2017). Examples of contemporary method includes but not restricted to Equated yield analysis, Rational valuation model and Real value or Equated yield (Jefferies, 2009). This work seeks to juxtapose traditional and contemporary methods of investment valuation. It pays particular attention to the ‘Conventional Approach’, commonly known as Term and Reversion (T&R) method which is a traditional form of valuation which uses All Risk Yield (ARY) or Initial yield (IY) approach and the modern or contemporary method which uses Equated yield in a Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method is the basis for juxtaposition towards an alternative approach.

II. Review of the Nature and Basis for Conventional and Contemporary Valuation

All Risk Yield or Initial Yield (k) is the conventionally analyzed yield commonly used under the traditional investment method of valuation. It is usually derived from the analysis of rental value and recently concluded sales of properties comparable to the one being valued.

Simply put, “an all risks yield ARY may be defined as a method that simply reflects implicitly all future benefits and disadvantages of an investment” (Fernandez, 2019).

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It is described as ‘all risk yield’ because it is presumed to have taken care of all aspects of risk associated with properties in an implicit manner. It is described as ‘all risk yield’ because it is presumed to have taken care of all aspects of risk associated with properties in an implicit manner. It is described as ‘all risk yield’ because it is presumed to have taken care of all aspects of risk associated with properties in an implicit manner (Fernandez, 2019).

$$k = \frac{\text{Current Rental Value}}{\text{Average Sales Price}} \times 100$$

Equated yield (e)

Equated yield is the yield that would equate the total cash inflows from an investment to the total cash outflows and at which net present value becomes zero which is similar to that of Internal Rate of Return (IRR). In conventional method we use (*k*) but in contemporary we adopt equated yield (*e*) in DCF approach and it is an in-built internal rate of return where is provision for annual rental growth (*g*).

Equated yield (*e*) is therefore the upward adjustment of all-risk yield (*k*) and the addition of (*k*) and the annual sinking fund required to replace capital at (*e*) over the review period (*t*) as follows;

$$e = k \{ 1 + \frac{g}{1 + k} \}^t$$

Discounted cash flow DCF is defined as, “the discounting of all future receipts and expenditures readily allowing for inflation, taxation and frequent changes” (Shapiro et al, 2009). All of these receipts and expenditures are added up to produce a cash flow sum that cash flow sum produces a value which a reasonable investor would expect to pay for a particular investment.

Annual Rental Growth (*g*) is another important variable that must be put in perspective especially when contemporary method of valuation is to be adopted. Annual rental growth is an inbuilt real growth rate of rental income from real estate investment; it is a factor of several variables including length of rent review and inflationary trend. It can only be determined by formula if not given thus;

$$(1 + g)^t = \frac{Y_p \text{ in Perp @ } e \times X - Y_p \text{ for } t \text{ years @ } k}{Y_p \text{ in Perp @ } e \times X - P_v \text{ for } t \text{ years @ } k}$$

$$\text{Or } (1 + g)^t = \frac{e - k}{ASF@e} + 1$$

DCF techniques is the valuation approach that takes into consideration the timing of cash inflow (income receipt) and cash outflow (expenditure) that will emanate from property investment by reducing them to present values. Cash flow table is normally prepared to reflect the pattern of periodic payment and receipt which will make it possible to incorporate variations in cash flows (Kruschwitz., & Löffler, 2006).

The traditional or conventional approach uses the ARY method through the summation of T&R Value to arrive at the capital value (CV). The value of T is calculated by capitalizing the net rental income at an appropriate rate over the unexpired period that the lease is to run while the R value is determined by capitalizing the net full rental value (FRV) of the property by years purchase in perpetuity deferred the period that must elapse before the reversion takes effect through the use of years purchase of a reversion to perpetuity table.

The valuers should give proper consideration to his client’s instructions in order to select the most appropriate method for the type of valuation he has been instructed to carry out.

Both of these methods will be used to undertake a valuation of a hypothetical property located in Abuja, Nigeria. The results of the valuation can then be correlated to solidify the three observations put forward by this paper.

Hypothetical Data for Valuation

A freehold interest in a tastefully furnished residential property leased for 35 years at a rent of ₦ 50,000:00 per annum on full repairing and insurance term with a provision for Seven yearly rent reviews. The Full Rental Value of the property is ₦ 90,000:00 p.a net. An identical property recently sold for ₦ 1,200,000. Given a redemption yield of 4% on government gilts, calculate the capital value by both the Conventional and Contemporary.

Method (x)

Valuation by the use of Conventional or Traditional Investment Method (Term and Reversion)

All Risk Yield or Initial Yield (k)

$$k = \frac{90,000}{1,200,000} \times 100 = 7.5\%$$

$k = 7.5\%$

TERM	
Rent Receivable	₦ 50,000
Yp for 7yrs @ 6.5%	5.4845
Value of term	₦ 274,225
REVERSION	
Full Rental Value (FRV)	₦ 90,000
Yp in perp @ 7.5% deferred 7yrs	0.0367
Value of Reversion	₦ 723,303
CAPITAL VALUE (CV)	₦ 997,528.00

Method (y)

Valuation by the use of Contemporary or modern Method (Equated Yield Analysis DCF)

Annual growth rate by the use of the 3-yp formula:

$$(1+g)^t = \frac{yp \text{ in perp. @ } k - yp \text{ for } t \text{ yr. @ } e}{yp \text{ in perp. @ } k \times Pv \text{ ₦ for } t \text{ yr. @ } e}$$

$$(1+g)^7 = \frac{yp \text{ in perp. @ } 7.5\% - yp \text{ for } 7 \text{ yrs. @ } 6\%}{yp \text{ in perp. @ } 7.5\% \times Pv \text{ ₦ for } 7 \text{ yrs. @ } 6\%}$$

$$(1+g)^7 = \frac{13.3333 - 5.5824}{13.3333 \times 0.6651}$$

$$(1+g)^7 = 1.0627$$

$$(1+g) = 1.0627^{1.75}$$

$$(1+g) = 1.1123$$

$$g = 1.1123 - 1$$

$$g = 0.1123 \text{ or } 11.23\%$$

(t) Review Period	(₦) Current Annual Rent	Amt N@(g) g factor@ 11.23%	(₦) Projected Income p.a	yp for t year @ (e)6%	(g@e) ⁻¹ Pv @ (e) 6%	Present Value of Cash Flow. (DCF)
0-7	50,000	1.00	50,000	5.5824	1.00	279,120
7-14	90,000	2.1065	189,585	5.5824	0.6651	703,901
14-21	90,000	4.4372	399,348	5.5824	0.4423	986,028
21-28	90,000	9.3468	841,212	5.5824	0.2942	1,381,558
28-35	90,000	19.6886	1,771,974	5.5824	0.1956	1,934,849
>35@perp	90,000	41.4732	3,732,588	13.3333	0.1301	6,474,780
Capital Value =						₦ 11,760,236:00

Total cash flow - Purchase cost = NPV
 ₦ 11,760,236:00 – ₦ 1,200,000 = ₦ 10,560,236

III. Findings and Results

Valuation through the use of the two methods have been illustrated above and we can see that both methods relies on assumptions in order for capital values to be calculated. Shapiro et al opined that, explicit assumptions must be made for contemporary approach by the use of DCF and implicit assumptions for the conventional approach

by the use of ARY all risks yield (Shapiro et al, 2009). Explicit meaning assumptions made clearly with little doubt and it is flexible to accommodate as much variables as necessary. Implicit being more suggestive and reasonable than verbatim. Implicit assumptions for example may include that the property is being sold at an arm's length transaction or that all legal documentation for the conveyancing is in place and there is nothing to hinder the property's value as a result. Implicit assumptions form part of the all risks yield, for example if there was a problem with the property legally or physically then there would be more risk and the all risks yield would be adjusted to reflect this. In the Term and Reversion T&R in (x) approach to the hypothetical question, it has been implicitly assumed that there are no such hindering physical or legal defects which could hurt the value of the property.

On the other hand, the discounted cash flow of Method (y) has explicitly assumed that the property will be occupied for the entire holding period of 35 years and that the growth rate determines to be 11.23%. which was arrived at by the use of 3-yp formula. The ability of valuers to set out all the necessary parameters towards arriving at accurate value can be problematic as Brown et al noted, "the test of valuation is more of forecasting ability of the valuer as it is about their ability to interpret information and data collected (Brown et al, 1998)." What Brown et al are implying on is that the valuer can only reasonably value a property if they have all of the information and facts. Explicit assumptions cannot be reasonably made for a long-term discounted cash flow as future events such as a change in market conditions are highly likely to occur, effecting growth rates and occupancy rates just to name a couple of examples. The RICS have also stated that, "forecasts of property market movements are incredibly difficult to make (RICS, 1997)." The case of *Singer and Freidlander Ltd v John D Wood and Co [1977 2 EGLR]* arose because of this assumption's dilemma. In this case a valuer was found negligent over his analysis of the information at his disposal and the assumptions made. The judge ruled that, "any valuation falling outside of a bracket (margin of error) brings into the question the competence of the valuer and the sort of care he gave to the task of valuation.

Both methods of valuation as demonstrated in Method (x&y) relied on the use of implicit and explicit assumptions. A valuer cannot be held negligent if market conditions changes, provided that the information and assumptions at the time of the valuation were accurate and clearly stated. However, there is a strong case to be made that explicit assumptions are riskier than implicit assumptions and valuers should exercise additional caution when undertaking discounted cash flows.

The second area this paper seek to address is the challenges posed by all risks yield. One issue with all risks yield approach is that it is implicit in nature, it is perceived not to take growth rate into account. As argued by Scarrett and Osborn who warn that the consequences of this is that it makes it "difficult to know the effect of any yield adjustment," (Scarrett and Osborne, 2008). One must disagree with this argument however, whilst it is agreed that implicit approaches are most restrictive, the valuer should still take into account the prospects of growth when calculating the all risks yield. A property with little prospect of growth will have a higher all risks yield to reflect the lower capital value, and vice versa for a good prospect of growth.

Discounted cash flows are more beneficial for growth focused investors as the growth rate can be accounted for with the cash flow model (Plenborg, 2002). As seen within the cash flow for method (y) example, the growth rate is likely to be wrong in the long term as Medium Term Treasury bonds are used as the benchmark in adjustment for the calculation. Bond markets or government gilts are not stable and although are less volatile than equities, they still change over time.

IV. Recommendations

The RICS make a strong point that, "one problem with the all-risks yield is the difficulty of assessing transaction evidence and making a suitable adjustment. Even a minor difference such as a rent review for one property being closer than that for another may make comparison difficult" (RICS, 1997). This is an important point raised by the RICS as in the case of method (x) example. An all risks yield of 8.5% will lower the capital value when compared to an all risks yield of 7.5%. Yet no valuer processes information in the same way and some may use a yield of 8.5% and still justify the valuation without any sign of negligence.

Just like in the term and reversion and the discounted cash flow the valuations are different. There are two reasons for this, firstly the term and reversion defers the reversionary value for 7 years which impacts heavily on value and secondly the discounted cash flow uses a discount rate of 11.23% compared with the all risks yield of 6.5% for the term and 7.5% for the reversion. Both of these values differ yet because they can be reasonably justified so neither one is wrong. This in turn identifies a problem, that two different methods can produce two different valuations. Scarrett agrees, he says "it is unlikely that two valuations would produce precisely the same

value, even if they do so the components would vary (Scarrett, 2015).”

It’s also equally important for the valuer to focus on the type of client he is working for and the purpose of the investing (Mun, 2012). In method (x) example in this work the worth of the investment is 1,200,000. Here the client wants a property that can provide steady and reliable cash flow over the duration of period.

The above point is in line with the third argument set out in this paper, both methods have their strengths and weaknesses and that’s not a bad thing. The reason why it’s acceptable for the methods to have pros and cons is because, “the valuation basis must be appropriate for the purpose of the valuation (RICS Global Standards, 2020).” The RICS have come to the conclusion that traditional methods are valuable and have their use but sometimes a discounted cash flow is more appropriate and valuers shouldn’t shy away from undertaking their use (Shapiro et al, 2009). The question comes down to, what is the purpose of the valuation? This is where the valuer must use his experience and judgment.

If the client is a complex institutional investor who wants a breakdown of cash flow, taxes and costs to calculate the worth or to compare the risk of one property with another through the IRR then the DCF is appropriate but if market value is sort then a T&R method is more appropriate.

One would argue in the case of method (x) that all risks yield method is more appropriate for the client’s circumstance, however it has been an interesting exercise to see how the DCF produces a different valuation and how that valuation of “worth” may be useful to a different client with different condition.

V. Conclusion

To conclude then, we need to remember as property professionals that, “all valuations are estimates and carried with them a degree of uncertainty” (French, & Gabrielli, 2005). We should not use assumptions that we cannot reasonably make or use market data that is incomplete or that cannot be understood. Valuers should not use inappropriate methods which fail to match the expectations of the client and their instructions.

This paper has intended to contribute to such a fascinating academic debate where literature is lacking. There has been very little attention paid by the academic community to this subject and one would hope that further future research is carried out.

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